

Short name	Transport modalities under the EU ETS	Long name	Unclear status of the various transport modalities for transportation of CO2 under the EU ETS
Geographical scope	EU member states		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>This issue manifests in EU member states, whereby lack of clarity as to the legal status of various modes of CO2 transportation, including liability questions, accentuates the challenges of pursuing cross-border CC(U)S cooperations, as well as national value chains.</p> <p>The CCS Directive defined 'transport networks' as "network of pipelines, included associated booster stations, for the transport of CO2 to the storage site". The ETS Directive only included pipelines in the ETS as the method of transporting CO2 for the purpose of storage; excluding all other transport modalities. This creates a 'gap' in the value chain, making it impossible to transport CO2 via ship or other modalities for storage and have the CO2 counted as not emitted under the ETS. The ETS Directive is, however, currently being revised to include other modes of transportation. This entail that the CO2 captured and transported via e.g. ship before being permanently stored can be counted as not emitted in the future.</p> <p>The ETS is currently the main policy instrument that incentivizes CC(U)S. Any uncertainty as to the eligibility of various transportation means can undermine the financial feasibility of CC(U)S projects. The issue stems in part from the need to maintain traceability and accurate quantification and verification methodologies of CO2 throughout the value chains.</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<p>Currently the EU ETS does not provide for any other transport modality than pipeline. There are, however, plans for this to be rectified such that transboundary CC(U)S activities may fully benefit from the incentivization of the EU ETS.</p> <p>Ships will be included from 2024.</p>		
Other issues this affects	Incentivization of CC(U)S, MRV, Liability		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Union (2003). Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 October 2003 establishing a scheme for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Community. Official Journal of the European Union, L 275/32. • European Commission (2019). European Green Deal. https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en • Council of the European Union (2022). Position of the Council (general approach) on the Revision of the EU Emissions Trading 		

	<p>System. https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-10096-2022-INIT/en/pdf</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• European Parliament (2022). Position of the European Parliament on the Revision of the EU Emissions Trading System. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2022-0246_EN.html
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